

Zeroing Dynamics-Based Stabilizing Controller Design of Diffusion-Reaction Systems

Ahmed MAIDI^{a,*}, Radoslav PAULEN^b, and Jean-Pierre CORRIOU^c

^a Laboratoire de Conception et Conduite des Systèmes de Production,
Université Mouloud MAMMERY, 15 000 Tizi-Ouzou, Algérie.

^b Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology,
Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Radlinského 9,
812 37 Bratislava, Slovakia.

^c Reaction and Process Engineering Laboratory,
UMR 7274-CNRS, Lorraine University, ENSIC
1, rue Grandville, BP 20451, 54001 Nancy Cedex, France.

August 19, 2025

Abstract: Stabilizing nonlinear distributed parameter systems within the framework of the late lumping approach is a challenging problem. Diffusion-reaction systems, described by semilinear partial differential equations, represent a common class of distributed parameter systems encountered in real applications. In this work, the zeroing dynamics method is used to design a stabilizing infinite-dimensional controller for this important class of systems. Both distributed and boundary actuations are investigated. The design of the controller relies on the concept of the characteristic index. In the case of distributed control, as the characteristic index is finite, the design is straightforward. However, in the case of boundary control, the characteristic index is infinite, thus an equivalent pointwise control form is derived to reduce it to a special case of distributed control, which enables the controller design. In the disturbance-free case, the developed controllers ensure exponential stability. In the presence of disturbances, the closed-loop system remains stable, and the steady-state error can be reduced to an arbitrarily small value by tuning the controller parameters. Four common application examples from the literature are provided to demonstrate the effectiveness of the developed controllers: the catalytic

*Corresponding author: ahmed.maidi@gmail.com

rod, the monoenzyme system, the heated rod, and the FitzHugh-Nagumo equation.

Keywords: distributed parameter system, diffusion-reaction system, semilinear parabolic partial differential equation, characteristic index, zeroing dynamics, boundary control, distributed control.

1 Introduction

The characteristics of variables (state, control, or output) in real dynamic systems are often inhomogeneous and exhibit spatio-temporal variations (Christofides, 2001a; Curtain and Zwart, 1995; Liu, 2010; Ray, 1989). Dynamic behavior of these systems, referred to as distributed parameter systems (DPSs) or infinite dimensional systems (Curtain and Zwart, 1995; Ray, 1989), is described by partial differential equations (PDEs), with an inherently infinite-dimensional state vector (Curtain and Zwart, 1995). Such systems arise in various domains, including chemical and thermal processes, mechanical systems, fluid flows, biological and biomedical systems.

Control theory plays a crucial role in efficient monitoring and performance enhancement of these systems. With the development of mathematical theories and the increasing power of computers, there has been a growing interest in the control of DPSs, which has led to extensive research (Christofides, 2001b; Meurer, 2013; Padhi and Faruque Ali, 2009). Numerous control approaches have been developed in the literature, which can generally be classified into early and late lumping approaches (Christofides, 2001a; Meurer, 2013; Ray, 1989).

Early lumping approach consists in reducing the PDEs to a set of ordinary differential equations, generally of high-dimension, either by approximating the PDEs or their solutions. See Li and Qi (2010) for a review of approximation and reduction methods. The objective of approximation is to leverage the powerful and well-developed control theory of lumped parameter systems (LPSs). The drawbacks of the early lumping approach lie in the high dimensionality of the resulting controller, which often lead to unacceptable performance and control quality due to approximation errors (Christofides and Daoutidis, 1996; Meurer, 2013). Moreover, closed loop stability may be affected by the spillover phenomenon due to the neglected modes. Additionally, the approximation process requires high computational effort, especially when the PDEs are nonlinear (Christofides, 2001a; Ray, 1989), and may obscure the fundamental control properties of the original DPS (Christofides, 2001a; Christofides and Daoutidis, 1996; Meurer, 2013; Ray, 1989; Singh and Hahn, 2007). On the other hand, the late lumping approach relies on the straightforward use of the original PDEs model without resorting to reduction or approximation of the DPS (Christofides, 2001a; Meurer, 2013; Ray, 1989). This allows taking into account the distributed nature of DPSs and enhances the control performance (Christofides, 2001a; Christofides and Daoutidis, 1996). In the case of linear DPSs, the abstract formulation of the PDEs (Curtain and Zwart, 1995) is used, and many concepts from LPS control theory can be generalized to DPSs thanks to the well-developed semigroup theory of linear operators (Curtain and Zwart, 1995). Drawbacks of the late lumping approach relate to the fact that the mathematical manipulation of PDEs is difficult and both analysis and design require sophisticated mathematical tools from functional analysis.

Many successful controllers with interesting applications, following either the early or the late lumping approaches, have been developed in the literature. A concise review can be found in (Christofides, 2001a,b; Meurer, 2013; Padhi and Faruque Ali, 2009). Although a considerable body of research exists, control design for nonlinear DPSs remains underexplored (Christofides, 2001a), very difficult, and it requires advanced mathematical techniques. For nonlinear DPSs, it is difficult to develop a unified control theory and the investigation is usually conducted on a case-by-case basis. Overall, nonlinear PDEs can be classified into semilinear, quasilinear, and fully nonlinear equations (Salsa, 2015). Semilinear parabolic PDEs are widely used to model diffusion-reaction systems, which represents an important class of DPSs, particularly in heat transfer, chemical engineering, fluid flows and biology (Christofides, 2001a; Kernevez and Thomas, 1975; Liu, 2010).

Control of diffusion-reaction systems has been extensively studied within the framework of early lumping approach (Christofides, 2001a; Pourkargar and Armaou, 2016; Wu and Li, 2008, 2009; Wu et al., 2016) and late lumping approach (Furtat and Gushchin, 2022; Li et al., 2011; Raab et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2012, 2017; Wu et al., 2014, 2018; Zhang et al., 2024). Notably, most contributions fall within the early lumping framework. Among those based on the late lumping approach, many resort to fuzzy modeling to leverage the well-established linear PDE control theory and address the challenges associated with nonlinearity (Raab et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2012; Wu et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2024). It must be noted that fuzzy modeling makes very little use of the knowledge of the fundamental model represented by its PDEs. In general, stabilizing nonlinear DPSs within the framework of the late lumping approach is a challenging problem.

The zeroing dynamics (ZD) method is a recently developed control approach (Zhang et al., 2020), which has demonstrated its efficiency in controlling LPSs (Ding et al., 2023; Hu et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2018; Zheng and Zeng, 2023). To the best of our knowledge, the only work that has applied this novel control approach to DPSs is that of Maida et al. (2024), where we used the ZD method to develop a velocity controller to address the control singularity encountered with geometric control. In Maida et al. (2024), it is demonstrated that, in addition to the notable performance of the ZD method, the controller design within the framework of the late lumping approach is a straightforward and simple task.

Motivated by the above considerations, the aim of this work is to extend the ZD method to develop simple and effective distributed and boundary controllers for diffusion-reaction systems described by a semilinear parabolic PDEs within the framework of the late lumping approach. We investigate both distributed and boundary control problems. The design of the controller relies on the concept of the characteristic index from geometric control of DPSs (Christofides and Daoutidis, 1996). The design is straightforward for the distributed control, since the characteristic index is finite. However, in the case of boundary control, as the characteristic index is infinite, we derive an equivalent pointwise control form to overcome the controllability problem (Maida and Corriou, 2011). We also demonstrate that the developed controllers ensure stability in the presence of bounded disturbances, and exponential stability in a disturbance-free scenario. We demonstrate the stabilization capability of the developed controllers using four applications examples (catalytic rod reactor, monoenzyme system, heated rod, and FitzHugh-Nagumo equation).

The contributions of the paper are as follows:

- We extend the zeroing dynamics method to design distributed and boundary stabilizing controllers for diffusion-reaction systems;
- We achieve the control design within the framework of the late lumping approach, i.e., using the PDE model directly;
- For the boundary control problem, we address the issue related to the infinite characteristic index by converting the problem into an equivalent pointwise control form;
- We carry out the stability analysis based on semigroup theory;
- We present four application examples, involving a catalytic rod, a monoenzyme system, heated rod, and the FitzHugh-Nagumo (FHN) equation, to demonstrate the efficiency of the developed controllers.

The structure of the article is as follows. Section 2 formulates the control problem addressed in this work. Section 3 explains the design of distributed and boundary controllers within the framework of the late lumping approach using the ZD method. Section 4 develops the stability analysis of the resulting closed loop system. Application examples, along with numerical simulation results, are presented in Section 5. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper.

Notation: In the following, \mathbb{R}^+ is the set of positive real numbers, \mathbb{R}^n is the n -dimensional Euclidean space equipped with the norm $\|\cdot\|$, $C(\overline{\Omega})$ is the space of continuous functions on the bounded domain $\overline{\Omega}$, and $H^n = [L^2(\overline{\Omega})]^n$ is a Hilbert space of n -dimensional square-integrable vector functions, equipped with the inner product (Zeidler, 1995),

$$\langle \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w} \rangle_{H^n} = \int_{\overline{\Omega}} \mathbf{v}^T \mathbf{w} \, dz; \quad \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w} \in H^n, \quad (1)$$

and the associated norm,

$$\|\mathbf{v}\|_{H^n} = \langle \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{v} \rangle_{H^n}^{1/2}. \quad (2)$$

2 Control problem statement

Consider the class of diffusion-reaction systems whose dynamic behavior is described by the semilinear parabolic PDEs with corresponding boundary conditions,

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}(z, t)}{\partial t} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{x}(z, t) + \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(z, t)) + \mathbf{B} (1 - \alpha) \mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{E} \mathbf{d}(t), \quad z \in \Omega, \quad (3)$$

$$L \mathbf{x}(z, t) = \mathbf{x}_0(t), \quad z = 0, \quad (4)$$

$$R \mathbf{x}(z, t) = \alpha \mathbf{u}(t) + (1 - \alpha) \mathbf{x}_l(t), \quad z = l, \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{x}(z, 0) = \boldsymbol{\varphi}(z), \quad z \in \overline{\Omega}, \quad (6)$$

where $t \in \mathbb{R}^+$ and $z \in \bar{\Omega}$ are the time and spatial variables, respectively. The set $\bar{\Omega} = [0, l]$ is the spatial domain of length l , i.e., $\bar{\Omega} = \Omega \cup \partial\Omega$ with $\Omega = (0, l)$ and $\partial\Omega = \{0, l\}$. The vector functions $\mathbf{x} \in H^n$, $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, and $\mathbf{d} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ are the state, control, and disturbance vectors, respectively, given as follows:

$$\mathbf{x} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ \vdots \\ x_n \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{u} = \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ \vdots \\ u_n \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{d} = \begin{bmatrix} d_1 \\ \vdots \\ d_n \end{bmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

The variables $\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{x}_l \in \mathbb{R}^n$ are the boundary condition vectors. The vector function $\boldsymbol{\varphi} \in H^n$ represents the initial spatial profile, and \mathbf{f} is a nonlinear vector function defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{f} = \begin{bmatrix} f_1 \\ \vdots \\ f_n \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

that satisfies $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{0}) = \mathbf{0}$. Thus, the term \mathbf{f} is the only nonlinear term in the model and defines its nonlinearity.

The operators \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{E} , \mathbf{L} , and \mathbf{R} are defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{A} = \text{diag} \left\{ D_1 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2}, \dots, D_n \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \right\}, \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \text{diag} \{ b_1(z), \dots, b_n(z) \}, \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{E} = \begin{bmatrix} d_{11}(z) & \dots & d_{1n}(z) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ d_{n1}(z) & \dots & d_{nn}(z) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{L} = \text{diag} \left\{ \frac{\partial^{k_1}}{\partial z^{k_1}}, \dots, \frac{\partial^{k_n}}{\partial z^{k_n}} \right\}, \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{R} = \text{diag} \left\{ \frac{\partial^{l_1}}{\partial z^{l_1}}, \dots, \frac{\partial^{l_n}}{\partial z^{l_n}} \right\}, \quad (13)$$

where D_i ($i = 1, \dots, n$) represent the diffusion coefficients, b_i ($i = 1, \dots, n$) are known functions that characterize the geometric structure of the actuators, d_{ij} ($i, j = 1, \dots, n$) are shape functions that characterize the spatial distribution of the disturbance d across the spatial domain Ω . The integers $k_i, l_i \in \{0, 1\}$ ($i = 1, \dots, n$), define the type of boundary condition. If k_i or l_i equals zero, the boundary condition is of Dirichlet type; if they equal one, the boundary condition is of Neumann type. The parameter α determines the type of actuation. Thus, when $\alpha = 0$, the actuation corresponds to the distributed control, while $\alpha = 1$ corresponds to the boundary control.

The control problem involves designing a distributed or boundary controller \mathbf{u} that stabilizes the

state \mathbf{x} at the equilibrium point $\mathbf{x}_e = \mathbf{0}$ or around it in the presence of the disturbance \mathbf{d} .

3 Distributed and boundary controllers design

In this section, we address the stabilization control problem within the framework of ZD control (Zhang et al., 2020; Zheng and Zeng, 2023). The design relies on the notion of the characteristic index (Christofides and Daoutidis, 1996), which generalizes the LPSs relative degree concept (Isidori, 1995) to DPSs. The proposed design approach can be applied to DPSs with a finite characteristic index. To solve the formulated stabilization problem, we propose to introduce the output vector,

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C} \mathbf{x}(z, t), \quad (14)$$

where the linear observation operator \mathbf{C} is given by:

$$\mathbf{C} = \text{diag} \{C_i, \dots, C_n\}, \quad (15)$$

and the integral operators C_i , ($i = 1, \dots, n$) are defined as follows:

$$C_i w(z, t) = \langle c_i(z), w(z, t) \rangle_{L^2(\bar{\Omega})} = \int_0^l c_i(z) w(z, t) dz, \quad (16)$$

where $c_i \in C(\bar{\Omega})$ ($i = 1, \dots, n$) are known functions that characterize the geometric structure of the sensors.

Thus, the operator \mathbf{C} acts on the state vector \mathbf{x} to produce the following output vector:

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} y_1(t) \\ \vdots \\ y_n(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \int_0^l c_1(z) x_1(z, t) dz \\ \vdots \\ \int_0^l c_n(z) x_n(z, t) dz \end{bmatrix}. \quad (17)$$

Assumption 1 *The continuous functions $c_i(z) \neq 0$ ($i = 1, \dots, n$) for $z \in \bar{\Omega}$.*

Assumption 2 *The disturbance \mathbf{d} is bounded, i.e., d_i ($i = 1, \dots, n$) are bounded.*

3.1 Distributed control

For the distributed actuation case, i.e., $\alpha = 0$, the DPS (3)–(5) reduces to:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}(z, t)}{\partial t} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{x}(z, t) + \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(z, t)) + \mathbf{B} \mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{E} \mathbf{d}(t), \quad z \in \Omega, \quad (18)$$

$$\mathbf{L} \mathbf{x}(z, t) = \mathbf{x}_0(t), \quad z = 0, \quad (19)$$

$$\mathbf{R} \mathbf{x}(z, t) = \mathbf{x}_l(t), \quad z = l, \quad (20)$$

$$\mathbf{x}(z, 0) = \boldsymbol{\varphi}(z), \quad z \in \bar{\Omega}. \quad (21)$$

To design the ZD distributed controller, we assume the following regarding the pair of functions b_i and c_i .

Assumption 3 *The functions b_i and c_i for $i = 1, \dots, n$ are not orthogonal, i.e., $\langle c_i(z), b_i(z) \rangle_{L^2(\bar{\Omega})} \neq 0$ for all $i = 1, \dots, n$.*

To solve the stabilization problem, within the framework of ZD method (Zhang et al., 2020), let us assume that $\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{0}$ and introduce the tracking error,

$$\mathbf{e}(t) = \mathbf{y}^d(t) - \mathbf{y}(t), \quad (22)$$

where \mathbf{y}^d is the vector of the desired references, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{y}^d(t) = \begin{bmatrix} y_1^d(t) \\ \vdots \\ y_n^d(t) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (23)$$

The design based on the ZD method consists in forcing the tracking error \mathbf{e} to decay exponentially to zero by imposing the following first-order dynamics on the error \mathbf{e} :

$$\dot{\mathbf{e}}(t) + \boldsymbol{\Lambda} \mathbf{e}(t) = \mathbf{0}, \quad (24)$$

with

$$\boldsymbol{\Lambda} = \text{diag} \{ \lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_n \}, \quad (25)$$

where $\lambda_i > 0$ ($i = 1, \dots, n$) are the tuning parameters of the controller.

Combining Eqs. (22) and (24) yields,

$$\dot{\mathbf{y}}^d(t) - \dot{\mathbf{y}}(t) + \boldsymbol{\Lambda} \mathbf{e}(t) = \mathbf{0}. \quad (26)$$

Using Eqs. (14) and (18), Eq. (26) reduces to:

$$\dot{\mathbf{y}}^d(t) - \mathbf{C} \mathbf{A} \mathbf{x}(z, t) - \mathbf{C} \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(z, t)) - \mathbf{C} \mathbf{B} \mathbf{u}(t) + \boldsymbol{\Lambda} \mathbf{e}(t) = \mathbf{0}. \quad (27)$$

For the distributed control problem, the operator \mathbf{CB} is given as follows:

$$\mathbf{CB} = \text{diag} \left\{ \int_0^l c_1(z) b_1(z) dz, \dots, \int_0^l c_n(z) b_n(z) dz \right\}, \quad (28)$$

and, since Assumption 3 ensures that the operator \mathbf{CB} is invertible, solving Eq. (27) with respect to the control \mathbf{u} yields the ZD distributed controller,

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = (\mathbf{CB})^{-1} (\dot{\mathbf{y}}^d(t) - \mathbf{CA} \mathbf{x}(z, t) - \mathbf{Cf}(\mathbf{x}(z, t)) + \mathbf{\Lambda} \mathbf{e}(t)). \quad (29)$$

3.2 Boundary control

For the boundary actuation case, i.e., $\alpha = 1$, the DPS (3)–(5) reduces to:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}(z, t)}{\partial t} = A \mathbf{x}(z, t) + \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(z, t)) + E \mathbf{d}(t), \quad (30)$$

$$L \mathbf{x}(z, t) = \mathbf{x}_0(z), \quad z = 0, \quad (31)$$

$$R \mathbf{x}(z, t) = \mathbf{u}(t), \quad z = l, \quad (32)$$

$$\mathbf{x}(z, 0) = \boldsymbol{\varphi}(z), \quad z \in \bar{\Omega}. \quad (33)$$

To design the ZD boundary controller, we assume the following regarding the functions c_i .

Assumption 4 *The functions c_i satisfy $c_i^{(k_i)}(l) \neq 0$, for $i = 1, \dots, n$.*

Remark 1 *For Dirichlet actuation, corresponding to $k_i = 0$, Assumption 4 is rendered redundant, as it is inherently satisfied by Assumption 1.*

For the boundary control problem (30)–(33), since the control acts at the boundary instead of within the PDEs, it is easy to conclude that the characteristic index does not exist, i.e., it is infinite (Maidi and Corriou, 2011). Thus, the ZD boundary controller cannot be designed. To address this controllability issue, we propose to derive an equivalent pointwise control form for the boundary control problem (30)–(33). This makes the control design straightforward as the equivalent pointwise control problem is a special case of the distributed control problem. The equivalent pointwise form can be easily derived using the Laplace transform (see Maidi and Corriou (2011) for details).

The equivalent pointwise control form of the boundary problem (30)–(33) represents a special case of the distributed control problem (18)–(21), where the control operator is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{B} = \text{diag} \{ D_1 \delta^{(1-k_1)}(z-l), \dots, D_n \delta^{(1-k_n)}(z-l) \}, \quad (34)$$

and accordingly, the ZD boundary controller is expressed as in Eq. (29), i.e.,

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = (\mathbf{CB})^{-1} (\dot{\mathbf{y}}^d(t) - \mathbf{CA} \mathbf{x}(z, t) - \mathbf{Cf}(\mathbf{x}(z, t)) + \mathbf{\Lambda} \mathbf{e}(t)). \quad (35)$$

Remark 2 Using the Dirac delta function property $\int_0^l g(z) \delta^{(r)}(z-l) dz = (-1)^r g^{(r)}(l)$ (Bronshtein et al., 2015), for the boundary control problem, it follows that,

$$\mathbf{CB} = \text{diag} \left\{ (-1)^{1-k_1} D_1 c_i^{(1-k_1)}(l), \dots, (-1)^{1-k_n} D_n c_n^{(1-k_n)}(l) \right\}. \quad (36)$$

Remark 3 The ZD controllers (29) and (35) with the operators (28) and (36), respectively, are derived assuming that the disturbance $\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{0}$. However, if \mathbf{d} can be measured or estimated using an observer, the performance in closed loop can be improved by taking into account the disturbance in controller design. In this case, the development outlined above results in the following ZD controller,

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = (\mathbf{CB})^{-1} (\dot{\mathbf{y}}^d(t) - \mathbf{CA} \mathbf{x}(z, t) - \mathbf{Cf}(\mathbf{x}(z, t)) - \mathbf{CE} \mathbf{d}(t) + \mathbf{\Lambda} \mathbf{e}(t)). \quad (37)$$

The operator \mathbf{CB} is given by Eq. (28) in the case of distributed control and by Eq. (36) in the case of boundary control.

Remark 4 If the disturbance d cannot be measured or estimated, its effect can be mitigated by appropriately tuning the parameters λ_i ($i = 1, \dots, n$) (see the proof given in the following section).

Remark 5 The proposed control laws (29) and (35) are derived based on the output tracking technique. Therefore, according to (14) and (22), the stabilization problem can be viewed as a special case of the tracking problem by choosing,

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \|\mathbf{y}^d(t)\| = \mathbf{0}, \quad (38)$$

or equivalently,

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} y_i^d(t) = 0, \quad i = 1, \dots, n. \quad (39)$$

4 Closed loop stability analysis

In this section, we investigate the stability of the DPS (3)–(5) equipped with either the distributed controller (29) or the boundary controller (35) under the unknown-but-bounded disturbance \mathbf{d} .

Theorem 1 The DPS (3)–(5), equipped with the ZD distributed controller (29) (or, respectively, with the ZD boundary controller (35)), is stable provided the Assumptions 1 and 2 are satisfied, i.e.,

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \|\mathbf{x}(z, t)\|_{H^n} \leq \varepsilon, \quad (40)$$

where ε is a small positive number, which can be made arbitrarily small by increasing λ^* defined as the minimum element of the set $\{\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_n\}$, i.e., $\lambda^* = \min\{\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_n\}$.

Proof 1 Let $\Delta \mathbf{y}$ be the deviation in the controlled output \mathbf{y} due to the bounded disturbance \mathbf{d} . In this case, Eq. (24) reduces to:

$$\dot{\mathbf{e}}(t) + \Delta \dot{\mathbf{e}}(t) + \mathbf{\Lambda} (\mathbf{e}(t) + \Delta \mathbf{e}(t)) = \mathbf{0}, \quad (41)$$

or equivalently,

$$\dot{\mathbf{e}}(t) + \mathbf{\Lambda} \mathbf{e}(t) + \boldsymbol{\vartheta}(t) = \mathbf{0}, \quad (42)$$

with $\boldsymbol{\vartheta} = \Delta \dot{\mathbf{e}} + \mathbf{\Lambda} \Delta \mathbf{e}$. Since \mathbf{d} is bounded, it follows that $\boldsymbol{\vartheta}$ is also bounded, i.e., $\|\boldsymbol{\vartheta}(t)\| \leq \vartheta_{\max}$.

The solution of Eq. (42) is given by:

$$\mathbf{e}(t) = \mathbf{T}(t) \mathbf{e}(0) + \int_0^t \mathbf{T}(t-s) \boldsymbol{\vartheta}(s) ds, \quad (43)$$

where $\mathbf{T}(t)$ is the semigroup generated by the matrix operator λ (Curtain and Zwart, 1995) given by Eq. (25) that satisfies the exponential growth $\|\mathbf{T}(t)\| \leq M e^{-\lambda^* t}$ with $M \geq 1$ and $\lambda^* = \min\{\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_n\}$.

We thus get,

$$\|\mathbf{e}(t)\| \leq M e^{-\lambda^* t} \|\mathbf{e}(0)\| + M \int_0^t e^{-\lambda^*(t-s)} \|\boldsymbol{\vartheta}(s)\| ds \quad (44)$$

$$\leq M e^{-\lambda^* t} \|\mathbf{e}(0)\| + M e^{-\lambda^* t} \int_0^t e^{\lambda^* s} \vartheta_{\max} ds \quad (45)$$

$$= M e^{-\lambda^* t} \|\mathbf{e}(0)\| + M e^{-\lambda^* t} \vartheta_{\max} \left(\frac{e^{\lambda^* t} - 1}{\lambda^*} \right) \quad (46)$$

$$= M \left(\|\mathbf{e}(0)\| - \frac{\vartheta_{\max}}{\lambda^*} \right) e^{-\lambda^* t} + \frac{M \vartheta_{\max}}{\lambda^*} \quad (47)$$

and, in consequence,

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \|\mathbf{e}(t)\| \leq \frac{M \vartheta_{\max}}{\lambda^*}. \quad (48)$$

Using Eqs. (17), (22), and (39), we can write Eq. (48) as:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \|\mathbf{y}(t)\| \leq \frac{M \vartheta_{\max}}{\lambda^*}, \quad (49)$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\int_0^l c_i(z) x_i(z, t) dz \right)^2} \leq \frac{M \vartheta_{\max}}{\lambda^*}, \quad (50)$$

which implies that the states x_i ($i = 1, \dots, n$) are bounded. Therefore, Eq (40) holds and the closed loop system is stable. Notably, according to Eq. (50), ε in Eq. (40) can be made arbitrarily small by increasing λ^* .

Theorem 2 The DPS (3)–(5), equipped with the ZD distributed controller (29) (or, respectively, with the ZD boundary controller (35)), is exponentially stable provided the Assumptions 1 and 2 are satisfied, i.e.,

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \|\mathbf{x}(z, t)\|_{H^n} = 0 \quad (51)$$

if the disturbance $\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{0}$.

Proof 2 The case of $\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{0}$ leads to $\boldsymbol{\vartheta} = \mathbf{0}$ in Eq. (42). Consequently, the bound $\vartheta_{\max} = 0$, and Eq. (50) simplifies to:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\int_0^l c_i(z) x_i(z, t) dz \right)^2 = 0. \quad (52)$$

Since the continuous functions c_i ($i = 1, \dots, n$) on $\bar{\Omega}$ satisfy Assumption 1, by applying the variational lemma (Zeidler, 1995, p. 117), we conclude that $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} x_i = 0$ ($i = 1, \dots, n$), i.e., Eq. (51) holds and implies that the closed loop system is exponentially stable.

5 Application examples

In this section, we consider four application examples to demonstrate the effectiveness of the developed ZD controllers. The first example involves stabilizing the temperature of a catalytic rod at its operating equilibrium point using either distributed or boundary controllers. The second example addresses the stabilization of substrate concentration in a membrane, despite the presence of an external uniformly distributed disturbance, by feeding an enzyme at the membrane in-domain. The third example concerns the stabilization of a heated rod using Dirichlet boundary actuation. The fourth example focuses on the boundary stabilization of a second-order DPS described by the FitzHugh-Nagumo (FHN) equation. The models are presented in dimensionless variables.

To achieve the stabilization objective, we choose the desired references y_i ($i = 1, \dots, n$) that satisfy condition (39) as follows:

$$y_i^d(t) = y_i(0) e^{-\omega t}, \quad (53)$$

where ω is a parameter used to fix the convergence rate and $y_i(0)$ is the initial condition of the controlled output y_i .

The closed loop system is simulated using the method of lines (Vande Wouwer et al., 2004) based on the finite difference schemes. The integral terms are approximated using the trapezoidal quadrature.

5.1 Catalytic rod reactor

Consider a long, thin, one-dimensional rod in a chemical reactor, where a zero-order exothermic reaction $\mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathcal{B}$ takes place (Christofides, 2001a; Qi et al., 2014; Ren et al., 2014). The rod exhibits an unstable operating equilibrium temperature $x_e = 0$. The control objective is to stabilize the rod using the developed ZD controllers. We consider both distributed and boundary control actuations. We assume that the physical parameters of both the rod and the reactor are constant.

5.1.1 Distributed control case

In the case of distributed control, the rod is not laterally insulated; i.e., it is in contact with the cooling medium of temperature u . The temperatures at both ends of the rod are specified as Dirichlet boundary

conditions. The dynamic behavior of the temperature x in the reactor obeys the following semilinear parabolic PDE (Christofides, 2001a),

$$\frac{\partial x(z, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{\pi} \frac{\partial^2 x(z, t)}{\partial z^2} + \beta_T (e^{-\gamma/(1+x(z,t))} - e^{-\gamma}) + \beta_U (b(z)u(t) - x(z, t)), \quad (54)$$

$$x(0, t) = 0, \quad (55)$$

$$x(l, t) = 0, \quad (56)$$

$$x(z, 0) = 0, \quad (57)$$

where β_T , γ and β_U represent the influences of heat of reaction, activation energy and heat transfer through the wall, respectively. Note that the temperature of the cooling medium u acting on the lateral surface of the rod represents a distributed control. The operating equilibrium temperature x_e of the rod is unstable, and due to the heat of the chemical reaction, the temperature of the reactor exhibits a hot-spot point at the middle of the rod (see Figure 1a). To stabilize the reactor temperature, we apply the ZD distributed controller (29), where the operator \mathbf{CB} is defined by Eq. (28). Thus, the ZD distributed controller takes the following form,

$$u(t) = \frac{\dot{y}^d(t) - \int_0^l c(z) \left(\frac{1}{\pi} \frac{\partial^2 x(z, t)}{\partial z^2} + \beta_T (e^{-\gamma/(1+x(z,t))} - e^{-\gamma}) - \beta_u x(z, t) \right) dz + \lambda (y^d(t) - y(t))}{\int_0^l c(z) b(z) dz}, \quad (58)$$

with $b(z) = c(z) = \sqrt{2/\pi} \sin(\pi z)$.

The simulation runs use the parameter values $\beta_T = 50$, $\beta_u = 2$, $\gamma = 2$, and $l = 1$ (Christofides, 2001a). We tune the controller so that the parameter $\lambda = 1$ and the rate constant $\omega = 2$. The obtained results given in Figure 1 clearly show that the distributed control achieves the control objective, i.e., it stabilizes the rod temperature at the equilibrium point $x_e = 0$ (Fig. 1d).

5.2 Boundary control case

In the boundary control case, the rod is in contact with the cooling medium at temperature x_e , and the left-hand end (at $z = 0$) of the rod is thermally insulated. The temperature of the rod is controlled at the right-hand boundary, i.e., at $z = l$, by manipulating the heat flux by means of the surrounding temperature u , which corresponds to a boundary control of Neumann type. In this case, the following

(a) Open-loop state profile.

(b) Evolution of output.

(c) Evolution of control.

(d) Closed loop state profile.

Figure 1: Distributed control of catalytic rod.

PDE model (Li et al., 2011) captures the evolution of the rod temperature:

$$\frac{\partial x(z, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{\pi} \frac{\partial^2 x(z, t)}{\partial z^2} + \beta_T (e^{-\gamma/(1+x(z, t))} - e^{-\gamma}) + \beta_U (x_c - x(z, t)), \quad (59)$$

$$\left. \frac{\partial x(z, t)}{\partial z} \right|_{z=0} = 0, \quad (60)$$

$$\left. \frac{\partial x(z, t)}{\partial z} \right|_{z=l} = u(t), \quad (61)$$

$$x(z, 0) = 0.2 \sqrt{\frac{z}{\pi}}. \quad (62)$$

Since the operating equilibrium temperature $x_e = 0$ is unstable as shown in Figure 2a, we use the ZD boundary controller (35) with the operator **CB** given by Eq. (36) to stabilize the rod temperature. This boundary controller takes the following form,

$$u(t) = \frac{\dot{y}^d(t) - \int_0^l c(z) \left(\frac{1}{\pi} \frac{\partial^2 x(z, t)}{\partial z^2} + \beta_T (e^{-\gamma/(1+x(z, t))} - e^{-\gamma}) - \beta_U (x_c - x(z, t)) \right) dz + \lambda ((y^d(t) - y(t))}{c(l)/\pi}. \quad (63)$$

with $c(z) = \sqrt{2/\pi} \sin(\pi z/2)$.

The simulation runs use the same physical parameters for the rod as in the previous distributed control case, along with the same decay rate ω . In the first simulation run, we consider that cooling medium temperature $x_c = 0$, and the controller tuning parameter $\lambda = 30$. From the obtained results given in Figure 2, we observe that the controller achieves the stabilization of the state x representing the rod temperature to the desired equilibrium point $x_e = 0$ (Fig. 2d).

The aim of the second simulation run is to evaluate the performance of the ZD boundary controller in response to variations in the cooling medium temperature x_c , which represent a disturbance. The disturbance considered is defined as follows:

$$x_c(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{for } t < 40, \\ 0.01 \sin(t - 40), & \text{for } t \geq 40. \end{cases} \quad (64)$$

Additionally, to assess the influence of the controller parameter, two values are considered: $\lambda = 1$ and $\lambda = 30$. The results are depicted in Figure 3. It can be concluded that as λ increases, the tracking error decreases, indicating improved regulation performance as shown by Figures 3a. This corroborates the result in Theorem 1 regarding the influence of the tuning parameter on the stabilization performance. We can also conclude that the ZD distributed controller with large tuning parameter λ achieves the stabilization of the state x representing the catalytic rod temperature around the equilibrium point $x_e = 0$ despite the persistent disturbance x_c given by (64) (Figs. 3c and 3d).

(a) Open-loop state profile.

(b) Evolution of output.

(c) Evolution of the control.

(d) Closed loop state profile.

Figure 2: Boundary control of catalytic rod without disturbance.

(a) Evolution of output.

(b) Evolution of control.

(c) Closed loop state profile ($\lambda = 1$).

(d) Closed loop state profile ($\lambda = 30$).

Figure 3: Boundary control of catalytic rod with disturbance.

5.3 Monoenzyme system

An enzyme distributed inside an artificial membrane controls the concentration of the substrate in the solution in which the membrane is immersed (Chen and Chang, 2009; Kernevez and Thomas, 1975). The following semilinear PDE (Chen and Chang, 2009; Kernevez and Thomas, 1975) captures the dynamic behavior of the substrate concentration in the membrane:

$$\frac{\partial x(z, t)}{\partial t} = D_s \frac{\partial^2 x(z, t)}{\partial z^2} - V_M \frac{x(z, t)}{K_M + x(z, t) + \frac{x^2(z, t)}{K_s}} + b(z) u(t) + d(z) d(t), \quad (65)$$

$$x(0, t) = 0, \quad (66)$$

$$x(l, t) = 0, \quad (67)$$

$$x(z, 0) = 0.3 \sin(\pi z), \quad (68)$$

where D_s , K_M , V_M are the substrate diffusion coefficient, the Michaelis constant, and maximum activity, respectively. The variables x , u , and d represent the substrate concentration, the added enzyme and the external bounded disturbance, respectively. We assume both u and d to be uniformly distributed in the membrane.

Without disturbance d , the monoenzyme system operates at the stable equilibrium point $x_e = 0$ (Fig. 4). However, due to the presence of the disturbance d (Chen and Chang, 2009), a controller should steer the concentration x to x_e . For this purpose, we use the ZD distributed controller (29) with the operator **CB** given by Eq. (28), which yields:

$$u(t) = \frac{\dot{y}^d(t) - \int_0^l c(z) \left(D_s \frac{\partial^2 x(z, t)}{\partial z^2} - V_M \frac{x(z, t)}{K_M + x(z, t) + \frac{x^2(z, t)}{K_s}} \right) dz + \lambda (y(t) - y^d(t))}{\int_0^l c(z) b(z) dz}, \quad (69)$$

with $b(z) = 1$, $c(z) = 1 + z$, and $d(z) = 1$.

The simulations use the following parameters: $l = 1$, $D_s = 0.5$, $V_M = 0.5$, $K_M = 1$, and $K_s = 1$ (Chen and Chang, 2009), and the decay constant $\omega = 2$. To assess the disturbance rejection capability of the ZD distributed controller, we define the external disturbance d as follows:

$$d(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & t < 10, \\ 10 \sin(t - 10) & t \geq 10, \end{cases} \quad (70)$$

and to show the influence of the tuning parameter λ on the regulation, we consider two values of the parameter $\lambda = 5$ and $\lambda = 10^3$.

The results are depicted in Figure 5. The same conclusion can be drawn about the influence of the tuning parameter on the stabilization performance. From Figs. 5c and 5d, it can be seen that as λ

Figure 4: Monoenzyme system: Open loop state profile without disturbance.

(a) Evolution of output.

(b) Evolution of control.

(c) Closed loop state profile ($\lambda = 5$).

(d) Closed loop state profile ($\lambda = 10^3$).

Figure 5: Distributed control of monoenzyme system.

increases, the tracking error decreases. We can also conclude that the ZD distributed controller with large tuning parameter λ achieves the exponential stabilization of the state x representing the substrate concentration to the equilibrium point $x_e = 0$ despite the disturbance d .

5.4 Unstable heated rod

Consider the boundary control of a thin metal rod of length $l = 1$, with the left-hand side $z = 0$ immersed in water at a given constant temperature, and the right-hand side $z = l$ inserted into a steam chest. The temperature at this end can be controlled by manipulating the steam pressure u , which corresponds to a Dirichlet actuation type (Ray, 1989). The heat flow x in the rod, which undergoes both diffusion along its length and heat loss to the surrounding medium across its lateral sides, is described by the dimensionless model (Krstic and Smyshlyaev, 2008; Ray, 1989):

$$\frac{\partial x(z, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 x(z, t)}{\partial z^2} - \beta x(z, t) \quad (71)$$

$$x(0, t) = 0 \quad (72)$$

$$x(l, t) = u(t) \quad (73)$$

$$x(z, 0) = 0.5 \sin(\pi z) \quad (74)$$

For values of $\beta \geq \pi^2/l$, the equilibrium $x_e = 0$ of the rod is unstable, as illustrated in Figure 6a for $\beta = 20$. To stabilize the rod, the ZD boundary controller (35), with the operator \mathbf{CB} defined by Eq. (36), is employed. This yields the following control law:

$$u(t) = \frac{\dot{y}^d(t) - \int_0^l c(z) \left(\frac{\partial^2 x(z, t)}{\partial z^2} - \beta x(z, t) \right) dz + \lambda (y(t) - y^d(t))}{\left. \frac{dc(z)}{dz} \right|_{z=l}} \quad (75)$$

with $c(z) = 1 - z$.

The simulation results obtained with the controller parameter $\lambda = 10$ and the rate constant $\omega = 2$ are shown in Figure 6. Clearly, it can be seen that the controller successfully stabilizes the rod temperature at the equilibrium $x_e = 0$ (Figure 6d), with reasonable control effort (Figure 6c).

5.5 FitzHugh-Nagumo equation

The FitzHugh-Nagumo (FHN) equation consists of two coupled semilinear PDEs, which are widely used to model the spatiotemporal dynamics of excitable systems encountered in biology and chemistry (Wang et al., 2012; Wu et al., 2014). These coupled PDEs describe the interaction between the concentrations

(a) Open-loop state profile.

(b) Evolution of output.

(c) Evolution of control.

(d) Closed loop state profile.

Figure 6: Boundary control of heated rod.

Figure 7: Boundary control of FHN equation: Open-loop profiles of states.

of two components, commonly referred to as the activator and the inhibitor, and are expressed as follows:

$$\frac{\partial x_1(z, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 x_1(z, t)}{\partial z^2} + x_1(z, t) - x_2(z, t) - x_1^3(z, t), \quad (76)$$

$$\frac{\partial x_2(z, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 x_2(z, t)}{\partial z^2} + v x_1(z, t) - \gamma x_2(z, t), \quad (77)$$

$$\left. \frac{\partial x_1(z, t)}{\partial z} \right|_{z=0} = \left. \frac{\partial x_2(z, t)}{\partial z} \right|_{z=0} = 0, \quad (78)$$

$$\left. \frac{\partial x_1(z, t)}{\partial z} \right|_{z=l} = u_1, \quad \left. \frac{\partial x_2(z, t)}{\partial z} \right|_{z=l} = u_2, \quad (79)$$

$$x_1(z, t) = 0.5 \cos(\pi z/2), \quad x_2(z, t) = 0.1 \cos(\pi z), \quad (80)$$

where x_1 and x_2 are the concentrations of the activator and the inhibitor, respectively. Note the strong nonlinearity due to x_1^3 in Equation (76) whereas Equation (77) is linear. The controls u_1 and u_2 manipulate the rate of change of concentrations x_1 and x_2 at the boundary $z = l$. v and γ are parameters of the system. The FHN equation involves an unstable equilibrium point at $\mathbf{x}_e = \mathbf{0}$ meaning that the concentration trajectories do not converge to x_e as t tends to infinity as shown in Figure 7. To force the concentrations to converge towards their equilibrium points, we use the controller (35) with the operator **CB** given by (36), which leads to the following ZD boundary controllers,

$$u_1(t) = \frac{\dot{y}_1^d(t) - \int_0^l c_1(z) \left(\frac{\partial^2 x_1(z, t)}{\partial z^2} + x_1(z, t) - x_2(z, t) - x_1^3(z, t) \right) dz + \lambda_1 ((y_1(t) - y_1^d(t)))}{c_1(l)}, \quad (81)$$

$$u_2(t) = \frac{\dot{y}_2^d(t) - \int_0^l c_2(z) \left(\frac{\partial^2 x_2(z, t)}{\partial z^2} + v x_1(z, t) - \gamma x_2(z, t) \right) dz + \lambda_2 (y_2(t) - y_2^d(t))}{c_2(l)}, \quad (82)$$

with $c_1 = c_2 = 1 + z$.

The simulation run uses the parameters $l = 1$, $v = 0.45$, $\gamma = 0.1$ (Wu et al., 2014). The parameters

Figure 8: Boundary control of FHN equation : Evolution of outputs.

Figure 9: Boundary control of FHN equation: Evolution of controls.

Figure 10: Boundary control of FHN equation: Closed loop profiles of states.

of the controllers are: $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = 50$, and decay rates $\omega_1 = \omega_2 = 0.5$. The obtained results, shown in Figure 10, demonstrate that the controllers exponentially stabilize the FHN equation as both states x_1 and x_2 , representing the activator and the inhibitor concentrations, respectively, converge to zero as t tends to infinity.

6 Conclusion

Using the ZD method, we have developed distributed and boundary stabilization controllers for a class of distributed parameter systems (DPSs) whose dynamic behavior is captured by semilinear parabolic PDEs, within the framework of the late lumping approach. The main idea behind the solution to the stabilization problem has been to introduce an output vector, whose components are defined as the weighted average of the DPS states. The stabilization problem is then reduced to driving the controlled output vector to zero. Since the ZD method is based on the tracking error dynamics, the characteristic index must be finite. It **has been** shown that, in the case of a distributed control, if the sensor and actuator functions are not orthogonal, the design is straightforward. However, in the case of boundary control, where the characteristic index is infinite, the boundary control is converted into a pointwise control problem, which is a special case of the distributed control. Assuming the sensor function does not vanish at the boundary, where the control acts, a ZD boundary controller has been designed in the same manner as in the distributed control case.

It **has been** demonstrated that both controllers ensure the stability of the closed-loop system in the presence of disturbance and that the steady-state error can be made arbitrarily small by an appropriate choice of the tuning parameters. In the absence of disturbance, the controllers achieve exponential stability. The stabilization capabilities of the developed controllers have been demonstrated through numerical simulations for common application examples from the literature: the catalytic rod, monoenzyme system, and FHN equation.

The ZD method is an effective and straightforward design approach for DPSs. This topic warrants further investigation; for instance, combining the controllers with a disturbance observer (see Remark 3) presents an intriguing direction for future work. Additionally, extending the ZD method to other classes of DPSs represents a promising research avenue, which we intend to address in future studies.

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